

Biographical Sketch: Ksenia Krasileva

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EDUCATION

PhD in Microbiology. Designated Emphasis in Computational Biology, **2005-2011**
University of California, Berkeley
Advisor: Dr. Brian Staskawicz.

Dissertation: “The Molecular Basis for Recognition of Oomycete Effectors in *Arabidopsis*.”

BS in Microbiology, Genetics and Plant Biology, Honors. **2001-2005**
University of California, Berkeley
Advisor: Dr. Steven Lindow.

Honors thesis: “Mechanisms of Quorum Sensing Inhibition in *Pseudomonas syringae* by Other Bacterial Epiphytes.”

EMPLOYMENT

Post-doctoral research associate **2011 – present**
Howard Hughes Medical Institute, University of California, Davis
Mentor: Dr. Jorge Dubcovsky.

Graduate Student Researcher, Graduate Student Instructor **2005-2011**
University of California, Berkeley

TEACHING

- **Undergraduate Research Mentor**, *University of California (UC) Berkeley*, 2007–2011
During my PhD, I mentored three undergraduate students, Margie Payumo, Connie Cheng and Kelsie Morioka. Margie and Connie spent at least two years in Brian Staskawicz’s lab, received undergraduate research awards and completed their Senior Thesis projects.
- **Guest Lecturer**, “Agriculture and Society”, *UC Berkeley*, 2008-2010
- **Teaching Assistant**, “Intro Programming for Bioinformatics”, *UC Berkeley*, 2007
- **Graduate Student Instructor**, Intro to Comparative Virology, *UC Berkeley*, 2007
- **Graduate Student Instructor** Introductory Biology (Outstanding GSI Award)
- **Course Instructor**, *Summer Explorations: 7-8th grades. UC Berkeley*, 2006
I was responsible for development and instruction of a summer course “Microbial Biology: Microbes, Health and Disease”, which included participation of about 20 middle school students.

OUTREACH

- **Panel Speaker**, *Biology Majors Fair*, 2007-2008
“Beyond the B.A.: Graduate and Professional Schools”
- **Volunteer in Community Outreach and Education**, 2006
“Agriculture, Molecular Biology and Genetically Modified Organisms: GMOs in Food”
Advanced training of UCCE Master Gardeners in Santa Clara County. Directed by regional outreach specialist Dr. Peggy Lemaux.

AWARDS

- 2007. UC Berkeley Outstanding Graduate Student Instructor Award.
- 2007. College of Natural Resources Conference Travel Award.
- 2006. NSF Honorable Mention.
- 2005. Departmental Citation for Graduation with Highest Honors.
- 2003-2005. Sponsored Projects for Undergraduate Research (SPUR).
- 2004. Summer Undergraduate Research Fellowship (University of California, Berkeley)

SOCIETIES

The International Society for Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions, 2009 – 2011.
American Association for the Advancement of Science, 2011-present.

PRESENTATIONS

2011. **Krasileva KV** “The Leucine-Rich Repeat Based Immunity: Mechanistic Insights into Recognition of Oomycete Effectors.” *Department of Plant Pathology, University of California, Davis* (Invited Seminar)
2010. **Krasileva KV**, Zheng C, Chou S, Alber T and Staskawicz BJ “RPP1-Mediated Immunity in *Arabidopsis thaliana* against *Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis*”. *Gordon Research Conference in Plant Molecular Biology*. Holderness, NH (Poster).
2009. **Krasileva KV**, Dahlbeck D and Staskawicz BJ. “Activation of the RPP1B-mediated innate immune response.” *International Symposium in Molecular Plant Microbe Interactions XIV Congress.*. Quebec, Canada (Talk).
2008. **Krasileva KV**, Dahlbeck D and Staskawicz BJ. “The Nature of Recognition of *Hyaloperonospora parasitica* effector ATR1 by *Arabidopsis thaliana*.” *Bay Area Microbial Pathogenesis Symposium*. University of California, San Francisco (Talk).
2008. **Krasileva KV**, Payumo MG, Dahlbeck D and Staskawicz BJ. “Recognition of *Hyaloperonospora parasitica* effector ATR1 by *Arabidopsis thaliana*.” *Keystone Symposium in Plant Innate Immunity*, Keystone, Colorado. (Poster)
2007. **Krasileva KV**, Win J, Kamoun S and Staskawicz BJ. “Computational Identification of Oomycete Effectors.” *Bay Area Microbial Pathogenesis Symposium*, University of California San-Francisco. (Poster)

PUBLICATIONS (2006-2011)

9 publications (4 as first/co-first author)

2012. Goritschnig S, **Krasileva KV**, Dahlbeck D, Staskawicz BJ. “Computational prediction and molecular characterization of an oomycete effector and the cognate Arabidopsis resistance gene” *PLoS Genetics* – *in press*.

2012. Win J, **Krasileva KV**, Kamoun S, Shirasu K, Staskawicz BJ, Banfield MJ. “Sequence divergent RXLR effectors share a structural fold conserved across plant pathogenic oomycete species” *PLoS Pathog* 8(1): e1002400.

2011. **Krasileva KV**, Zheng C, Leonelli L, Goritschnig S, Dahlbeck D, Staskawicz BJ. “Global analysis of *Arabidopsis* / downy mildew interactions reveals prevalence of incomplete resistance and rapid evolution of pathogen recognition” *PLoS One*, 6: e28765.

2011. Zhao B, Dahlbeck D, **Krasileva KV**, Fong RW, Staskawicz BJ. “Computational and Biochemical Analysis of the Xanthomonas Effector AvrBs2 and Its Role in the Modulation of Xanthomonas Type Three Effector Delivery.” *PLoS Pathog*. 12 :e1002408.

2011. Chou S*, **Krasileva KV***, Holton J, Steinbrenner A, Alber T, Staskawicz BJ. “*Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis* ATR1 effector is a repeat protein with distributed recognition surfaces” *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 108(32): 13323-8.

***authors contributed equally to this work**

2011. Potnis N*, **Krasileva K***, Chow V, Almeida NF Jr, Patil PB, Ryan RP, Sharlach M, Behlau F, Dow JM, White FF, Preston JF, Vinatzer BA, Koebnik R, Setubal JC, Norman DJ, Staskawicz BJ, Jones JB. Comparative Genomics Reveals Diversity among Xanthomonads Infecting Tomato and Pepper. *BMC Genomics*, 12(1): 146.

***authors contributed equally to this work**

2010. **Krasileva KV**, Dahlbeck D, Staskawicz BJ. Activation of an *Arabidopsis* Resistance Protein Is Specified by the *in Planta* Association of Its Leucine-Rich Repeat Domain with Cognate Oomycete Effector. *Plant Cell*, 22:1-16.

2010. Dulla GF, **Krasileva KV**, Lindow SE. Interference of Quorum Sensing in *Pseudomonas syringae* by Bacterial Epiphytes that Limit Iron Availability. *Environmental Microbiology*, 12(6): 1762-74.

2007. Win J, Morgan W, Bos J, **Krasileva KV**, Cano LM, Chaparro-Garcia A, Ammar L, Staskawicz BJ, Kamoun S. Adaptive Evolution Has Targeted the C-terminal Domain of the RXLR Effectors of Plant Pathogenic Oomycetes. *Plant Cell*, 19: 2349-69.